

Pre-Experiment Questionnaire

1. What is your main track of studies?
 - a. Single track – General
 - b. Single track – AI specialization
 - c. Single track – IS Development specialization
 - d. Double track
 - e. Other...
2. How would you rate your familiarity with the domain of elevators (for example, how elevators operate, typical functionalities, common issues)?
 - a. Not familiar at all
 - b. Beginner
 - c. Intermediate
 - d. Advanced
3. How would you rate your knowledge in software modeling?
 - a. No knowledge
 - b. Beginner
 - c. Intermediate
 - d. Advanced
4. How would you rate your experience with software modeling?
 - a. No experience
 - b. A few months
 - c. More than one year
5. How would you rate your familiarity with UML?
 - a. Not familiar at all
 - b. Slightly familiar
 - c. Moderately familiar
 - d. Very familiar
 - e. Extremely familiar
6. How would you rate your familiarity with Visual Paradigm?
 - a. Never used the tool
 - b. Beginner
 - c. Intermediate
 - d. Advanced
7. How would you rate your knowledge in programming?
 - a. No knowledge

- b. Beginner
 - c. Intermediate
 - d. Advanced
8. How would you rate your experience with programming?
- a. No experience
 - b. A few months
 - c. 1-5 years
 - d. More than 5 years
9. How would you rate your familiarity with Java?
- a. Not familiar at all
 - b. Slightly familiar
 - c. Moderately familiar
 - d. Very familiar
 - e. Extremely familiar
10. How would you rate your familiarity with Eclipse?
- a. Never used this tool
 - b. Beginner
 - c. Intermediate
 - d. Advanced